

Supplementary Material 1

Relative body length model description, checks, and diagnostics

Allegue H., Guinet C., Patrick S.C., Ribout C., Bichet C., Lepais O., Réale D.. *Offspring sex ratio increases with paternal reproductive success in a colony of southern elephant seals.*

Contents

1	The model equation	1
2	Prior predictive checks	2
3	Fit the model with brms	2
3.1	brms output summary	5
4	Visualizing MCMC draws and diagnostics	6
5	Posterior predictive checks	9

In this study, we estimated the seal relative body length from photogrammetry. We used a random intercept linear model with the repeated measurements of the seal body length as the response variable and the individual identifier as random intercept (Section 1), which we fitted in a Bayesian framework with the R package `brms` (Bürkner, 2017). We extracted the posterior distributions of the best linear unbiased predictors as the estimated relative body length of each seal.

In this document, we present the model equation (Section 1), the prior predictive checks (Section 2), the fitted model and its output (Section 3), the diagnostics for the MCMC sampling draws (Section 4), and the posterior predictive checks (Section 5). Overall, the various checks and diagnostics do not show any particular concerns with the model.

1 The model equation

$$\begin{aligned}y_{ij} &= \beta_0 + u_{0j} + \epsilon_{ij} \\u_{0j} &\sim \text{normal}(0, \sigma_{u_0}^2) \\ \epsilon_{ij} &\sim \text{normal}(0, \sigma_{\epsilon}^2)\end{aligned}$$

y_{ij} is the body length of the seal j for the observation i , β_0 is the mean population body length, u_{0j} is the deviation of individual j from the population mean β_0 which follows a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a variance of $\sigma_{u_0}^2$, and ϵ_{ij} is the residual value which follows a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a variance of σ_{ϵ}^2 .

2 Prior predictive checks

As we are interested in estimating the relative body length of each seal, we normalized the measured body length values (i.e., mean centered and unit variance) to help with prior specification. Therefore, the mean relative body length should be 0 (β_0). From previous studies that estimated body length from photogrammetry (e.g., Modig, 1996; Carlini et al., 2006), we know that most of the variance is explained by the among-individual variance ($\sigma_{u_0}^2$) and very little by the within-individual variance (σ_ϵ^2) because body length is highly repeatable. Therefore, $\sigma_{u_0}^2$ should be close to 1 and σ_ϵ^2 way smaller than $\sigma_{u_0}^2$. As the `brms` package models variances as standard deviations, we defined prior distributions for β_0 , σ_{u_0} and σ_ϵ as follow:

$$\beta_0 \sim \text{normal}(0, 0.05)$$

$$\sigma_{u_0} \sim \text{gamma}(10, 10)$$

$$\sigma_\epsilon \sim \text{gamma}(1, 5)$$

Figure S1: The histograms of the prior distributions of each of the model parameters: (β_0) the intercept, (σ_{u_0}) the among-individual standard deviation, and (σ_ϵ) the within-individual (residual) standard deviation.

Figure S2: Density function of the observed data overlaid to 100 simulated prior predictive distributions.

3 Fit the model with brms

We load the data of 80 individuals into the variable `dat` from the file `data_body_length.txt`, which can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7418941>

- `Id`: the seal unique identifier
- `Name`: the seal unique name
- `Photo_date`: the date at which the photo was taken
- `Scale_length_cm`: the length of the reference scale in centimeters
- `Scale_length_px`: the length of the reference scale in pixels
- `Length_px`: the length of the seal in pixels

- Length_cm: the length of the seal in centimeters

Figure S3: The date at which the photos of each male southern elephant seal (n = 80) were taken in 2017. The number of photos taken of each seal is provided between parentheses next to the name of the seal.

```

## scale body length
dat$Length_cm <- scale(dat$Length_cm)

# load brms R package (v2.15.0)
library("brms")

# define priors
bprior <- prior(normal(0, 0.05), class = "Intercept") +
  prior(gamma(10, 10), class = "sd") +
  prior(gamma(1, 5), class = "sigma")

# fit the model
fit <- brm(

  Length_cm ~ 1 + (1|Id),

  data      = dat,
  prior     = bprior,
  chain     = 4,
  core     = 4,
  iter      = 1e+05,
  thin      = 20,
  seed     = 555)

```

3.1 brms output summary

No divergent transitions were reported when fitting the model with the function `brm()`.

```

## Family: gaussian
## Links: mu = identity; sigma = identity
## Formula: Length_cm ~ 1 + (1 | Id)
## Data: body (Number of observations: 187)
## Samples: 4 chains, each with iter = 1e+05; warmup = 50000; thin = 20;
##           total post-warmup samples = 10000
##
## Group-Level Effects:
## ~Id (Number of levels: 80)
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## sd(Intercept)    1.00     0.08    0.85    1.17 1.00    9039    9381
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept    -0.01     0.05   -0.10    0.08 1.00    9745    9507
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## sigma        0.25     0.02    0.22    0.29 1.00    9913    9650
##
## Samples were drawn using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).

```


Figure S4: Density functions of the posterior distributions overlaid to the prior distributions for each of the model parameters: (b_Intercept) the intercept, (sd_Id__Intercept) the among-individual standard deviation, and (sigma) the within-individual (residual) standard deviation.

4 Visualizing MCMC draws and diagnostics

Figure S5: Time series (trace plot) of each of the Markov chains for each of the model parameters: (b_Intercept) the intercept, (sd_Id__Intercept) the among-individual standard deviation, and (sigma) the within-individual (residual) standard deviation.

Figure S6: The potential scale reduction statistic ($split - \hat{R}$) which measures the ratio of the variance of draws within each chain to the variance of all draws across chains (Gelman et al., 2013) for each of the model parameters: ($b_Intercept$) the intercept, ($sd_Id_Intercept$) the among-individual standard deviation, and ($sigma$) the within-individual (residual) standard deviation. If all chains converged similarly, these will be the same and \hat{R} will be one. If the chains have not converged to a common distribution, the \hat{R} statistic will be greater than one.

Figure S7: Histograms of the marginal posterior distribution (along the diagonal) of each of the model parameters : ($b_Intercept$) the intercept, ($sd_Id_Intercept$) the among-individual standard deviation, and ($sigma$) the within-individual (residual) standard deviation. Bivariate plots are displayed as hex plots above (2 Markov chains) and below (2 other Markov chains) the diagonal.

Figure S8: Overlaid histograms of the (centered) marginal energy distribution π_E and the first-differenced distribution $\pi_{\Delta E}$ for each of the Markov chains. Ideally both histograms should look the same (Betancourt, 2018).

Figure S9: The ratio of the effective sample size (N_{eff}) to the total sample size (N) for each of the model parameters: (`b_Intercept`) the intercept, (`sd_Id_Intercept`) the among-individual standard deviation, and (`sigma`) the within-individual (residual) standard deviation. The effective sample size is an estimate of the number of independent draws from the posterior distribution of the estimate of interest. The larger the ratio of N_{eff} to N the better (Gelman et al., 2013).

Figure S10: The autocorrelation (up to a lag of 10) of each of the Markov chains for each of the model parameters: (b_Intercept) the intercept, (sd_Id_Intercept) the among-individual standard deviation, and (sigma) the within-individual (residual) standard deviation.

5 Posterior predictive checks

Figure S11: Density function of the observed data overlaid to 100 simulated posterior predictive distributions.

Figure S12: Scatter plot of the observed data as a function of the average of 100 simulated posterior predictive distributions.

References

- Betancourt, M. (2018). A Conceptual Introduction to Hamiltonian Monte Carlo.
- Bürkner, P.-C. (2017). brms : an R package for Bayesian multilevel models using Stan. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 80(1):1–28.
- Carlini, A. R., Poljak, S., Daneri, G. A., Márquez, M. E. I., and Negrete, J. (2006). The dynamics of male harem dominance in southern elephant seals (*Mirounga leonina*) at the South Shetland Islands. *Polar Biology*, 29(9):796–805.
- Gelman, A., Carlin, J. B., Stern, H. S., Dunson, D. B., Vehtari, A., and Rubin, D. B. (2013). *Bayesian Data Analysis*. CRC Press., Boca Raton, FL, third edit edition.
- Modig, A. (1996). Effects of body size and harem size on male reproductive behaviour in the southern elephant seal. *Animal Behaviour*, 51(6):1295–1306.